
**AN EXPLORATORY STUDY OF THE CONTRIBUTION OF HIGHER
EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN UTTAR PRADESH TO THE
SHODHGANGA REPOSITORY**

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Abstract

This study investigates the contribution of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Uttar Pradesh to the Shodhganga repository, India's national digital platform for hosting electronic theses and dissertations (ETDs). Despite the growing emphasis on open access and digital archiving, participation in Shodhganga remains uneven across the state. As of 15 March 2023, only 60 out of 92 HEIs in Uttar Pradesh were found to be contributing to Shodhganga, revealing a notable participation gap. While most of the state public and central universities have been consistently submitting ETDs, many Institutes of National Importance and few state public and private universities have either delayed participation or have yet to sign the required Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with INFLIBNET. Using data retrieved from the AISHE portal and the Shodhganga website, this exploratory study analyzes institutional contributions based on type, district location, volume, and frequency of submissions. The results show that State Public Universities dominate the ETD contributions, followed by Central Universities, while private and deemed universities exhibit significantly lower participation. A time-gap analysis further reveals that although a majority of HEIs have submitted theses recently, a few institutions show extended periods of inactivity ranging from several months to over two years. The study underscores that INFLIBNET must engage more HEIs in the state through proactive outreach, while UGC and university authorities should strengthen policy measures and mandate timely ETD deposits. This study highlights both the achievements and shortfalls in Uttar Pradesh's engagement with Shodhganga and calls for more structured efforts to ensure inclusive and consistent participation.

Keywords: Shodhganga, Electronic Thesis and Dissertation (ETD), Uttar Pradesh, National Repository, INFLIBNET

1. Introduction

In the evolving landscape of academic research, the dissemination and accessibility of doctoral and postgraduate research have become increasingly important. Electronic Theses and Dissertations (ETDs) are now widely regarded as a vital source of original academic work and knowledge creation. In India, the Shodhganga repository, maintained by the INFLIBNET Centre under the University Grants Commission (UGC), serves as a national digital repository for hosting full-text ETDs submitted by recognized Indian universities (Gupta & Gupta, 2014). The Shodhganga initiative aims to ensure open access to Indian theses and dissertations, enhance research visibility, and prevent duplication of scholarly work. Participation in Shodhganga is

mandated for UGC-recognized universities, making it an essential parameter for evaluating the research output and compliance of higher education institutions (HEIs) (*About Shodhganga: A Reservoir of Indian Theses, INFLIBNET Centre, 2023*). The Shodhganga has emerged as the platform to Indian research scholars where they can showcase their one of the most prime research projects of their career i.e., their Ph.D. thesis and dissertation to the entire world and can contribute to developing a vast knowledge pool.

The state of Uttar Pradesh, being one of India's most populous and educationally diverse states, is home to a large number of HEIs across public, private, central, and deemed categories. According to the data retrieved from AISHE (All India Survey of Higher Education) there are 92 HEIs in the state. Despite this academic density, a systematic assessment of these institutions' contributions to the Shodhganga repository has not been thoroughly explored. This study aims to fill this gap by examining the extent and nature of ETD contributions made by HEIs of Uttar Pradesh to Shodhganga, thereby offering insights into research dissemination practices within the state.

2. Review of Literature

Several studies have investigated the institutional, regional, and national participation and contribution in electronic theses repositories in India. Jhamb and Samim (2017) analyzed the contribution of central universities of India to the Shodhganga repository and found that, out of 46 central universities, only 25 had signed the MoU and were actively contributing. In their study, Aligarh Muslim University of Uttar Pradesh emerged as the leading contributor with 6,458 ETDs, followed by Jawaharlal Nehru University with 4,693 ETDs. Their analysis also highlighted significant disciplinary variations in submissions, indicating that the majority of contributions came from the fields of Science and Social Sciences. Furthermore, the study emphasized that not all central universities were consistently uploading theses to Shodhganga and recommended that these institutions be encouraged to participate more actively. In another focused study, Das and Chauhan (2019) examined the contribution of state universities in Gujarat to the Shodhganga repository. They found that Maharaja Sayajirao University had submitted the highest number of ETDs (3,545), followed by Gujarat University with 3,334 ETDs. Most of the theses were submitted in English, followed by Gujarati. Their findings revealed a similar pattern of disproportionate participation, with only a few state universities contributing actively to the repository.

On a broader, regional level, Esh and Ghosh (2021) studied the contribution of Northeastern universities to the Shodhganga repository. Their analysis revealed that eight states of the Northeast region, comprising 67 higher education institutions (HEIs), had collectively submitted 13,088 ETDs. Among them, Assam accounted for the majority (63.21%), followed by Meghalaya (17.43%). The study raised concerns that although most universities in the Northeast had signed the MoU with INFLIBNET, only a limited number were actively uploading their theses. They concluded that the overall contribution of Northeastern universities to Shodhganga remained insufficient. At the national level, Singh (2019) reported that a total of 423 universities had signed the MoU with INFLIBNET for ETD submission to Shodhganga. However, by December 2018, only 381 were actually contributing. This gap indicates that, despite signing the agreement, a considerable number of universities had yet to actively participate in uploading their theses to the repository. Similarly, several case-specific studies have also been conducted to map institutional-

level and field specific engagement with Shodhganga. These include analyses of the ETD contributions of central universities in the Library and Information Science domain (Verma et al., 2017), contribution by Indian law universities (Siddiqui, 2020), a study of ETD submissions by Osmania University (Sandhya, 2019), as well as examinations of contributions made by state universities in West Bengal (Dey & Das, 2021) and Karnataka (Katagi & Kumbar, 2022).

While these studies contribute to understanding institutional, regional, and national trends, there remains a lack of focused research on state-level participation, particularly for Uttar Pradesh. Given the size, diversity, and research output of the state, a dedicated analysis is essential to identify institutional engagement patterns and areas of improvement in ETD contributions.

3. Objectives of the Study

The study aims to explore the contribution of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Uttar Pradesh to the Shodhganga repository. The specific objectives are:

1. To recognize the overall contribution made by HEIs of Uttar Pradesh to Shodhganga, the national digital repository of Indian electronic theses and dissertations (ETDs).
2. To analyze the distribution of contributions across different categories of HEIs namely, state public universities, central universities, private universities, and deemed-to-be universities.
3. To identify the top 10 contributing HEIs among all participating institutions from Uttar Pradesh.
4. To determine the maximum and minimum time gaps observed in the uploading of ETDs by various HEIs in the state.

4. Methodology

The present study is based on secondary data retrieved from two publicly available sources: the Shodhganga repository (About Shodhganga: A Reservoir of Indian Theses, INFLIBNET Centre, 2023) and the All-India Survey on Higher Education portal (AISHE- Higher Education Institution Directory, 2023). To identify the Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) located in Uttar Pradesh, the AISHE Directory of Institutions was consulted. This directory served as the authoritative list of HEIs recognized by regulatory bodies during the reference period.

The contribution data i.e., the number of Electronic Theses and Dissertations (ETDs) submitted by each HEI was then manually retrieved from the Shodhganga repository. The analysis is confined to data available up to 15 March 2023, and any submissions made after this date are excluded from the scope of this study. According to the AISHE directory, 92 HEIs are listed under Uttar Pradesh (U.P.). However, only 60 HEIs were found to have contributed ETDs to the Shodhganga repository as of the cut-off date (see Table 1). Hence, the analysis in this study is based solely on these 60 contributing institutions.

Table 1 Type and number of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Uttar Pradesh and their contribution status to the Shodhganga repository

Type of Higher Educations Institutions (HEIs)	No. of HEIs in U.P.	No. of HEIs Contributing ETDs to Shodhganga
Central University (CU)	6	4
Deemed University-Government (DUG)	2	0
Deemed University-Government Aided (DUGA)	3	2
Deemed University-Private (DUP)	4	4
Institute of National Importance (IoNI)	11	6
Institute under State Legislature Act (IuSLA)	1	0
State Open University (SOU)	1	1
Private University (PU)	32	24
State Public University (SPU)	32	19
Grand Total	92	60

Descriptive statistical methods have been used to analyze the data, with emphasis on institutional type (state, central, private, or deemed), frequency of contribution, and time gaps in thesis uploads.

5. Analysis and Results

5.1 Overall ETD contributions by HEIs of Uttar Pradesh to Shodhganga repository

Of the total 92 Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Uttar Pradesh listed in the AISHE directory, only 60 were found to be contributing Electronic Theses and Dissertations (ETDs) to the Shodhganga repository and remaining do not have their profile either such as Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, Sanjay Gandhi Post Graduate Institute of Medical Sciences and Khwaja Moinuddin Chishti Bhasha Vishwavidyalaya, Lucknow and including others. Table 2 presents a district-wise distribution of these 60 contributing HEIs along with the total number of ETDs submitted by each institution as of the data cut-off date, 15 March 2023.

Table 2 District-wise distribution of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Uttar Pradesh submitting ETDs to the Shodhganga repository.

S. No.	HEI Name	Type	District	No. of ETDs
1	Dayalbagh Educational Institute (Id: U-0507)	DUGA	Agra	1123
2	Dr. B. R. Ambedkar University (Id: U-0509)	SPU	Agra	5654
3	Aligarh Muslim University (Id: U-0496)	CU	Aligarh	9435
4	Mangalayatan University (Id: U-0528)	PU	Aligarh	95

5	Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Petroleum Technology (Id: U-0535)	IoNI	Amethi	36
6	Shri Venkateshwara University (Id: U-0611)	PU	Amroha	2
7	Acharya Narendra Deva University of Agriculture & Technology (Id: U-0531)	SPU	Ayodhya	634
8	Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia Awadh University (Id: U-0510)	SPU	Ayodhya	4622
9	Shri Ramswaroop Memorial University (Id: U-0753)	PU	Barabanki	95
10	Bareilly International University (Id: U-0897)	PU	Bareilly	1
11	Mahatama Jyotiba Phule Rohikhand University (Id: U-0525)	SPU	Bareilly	1419
12	Amity University (Id: U-0497)	PU	Gautam Buddha Nagar	1016
13	Bennett University (Id: U-0890)	PU	Gautam Buddha Nagar	16
14	Galgotias University (Id: U-0643)	PU	Gautam Buddha Nagar	51
15	Gautam Buddha University (Id: U-0514)	SPU	Gautam Buddha Nagar	195
16	IILM University (Id: U-1219)	PU	Gautam Buddha Nagar	2
17	Jaypee Institute of Information Technology (Id: U-0522)	DUP	Gautam Buddha Nagar	289
18	Noida International University (Id: U-0533)	PU	Gautam Buddha Nagar	56
19	Sharda University (Id: U-0541)	PU	Gautam Buddha Nagar	183
20	Shiv Nadar University (Id: U-0642)	PU	Gautam Buddha Nagar	139
21	Academy Of Scientific & Innovative Research (Id: U-0713)	IoNI	Ghaziabad	1719
22	Monad University (Id: U-0644)	PU	Ghaziabad	36
23	Santosh University (Id: U-0539)	DUP	Ghaziabad	105
24	Deen Dayal Upadhyay Gorakhpur University (Id: U-0508)	SPU	Gorakhpur	827
25	Madan Mohan Malaviya University of Technology (Id: U-0739)	SPU	Gorakhpur	65
26	Bundelkhand University (Id: U-0502)	SPU	Jhansi	2213
27	Chandra Shekhar Azad University of Agriculture & Technology (Id: U-0504)	SPU	Kanpur Nagar	70
28	Chatrapati Sahuji Maharaj Kanpur University (Id: U-0505)	SPU	Kanpur Nagar	10131
29	Harcourt Butler Technical University (Id: U-0864)	SPU	Kanpur Nagar	6

30	Rama University (Id: U-0808)	PU	Kanpur Nagar	45
31	Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University (Id: U-0498)	CU	Lucknow	508
32	Babu Banarsi Das University (Id: U-0499)	PU	Lucknow	54
33	Dr.A.P.J. Abdul Kalam Technical University (Id: U-0549)	SPU	Lucknow	302
34	Dr. Ram Manohar Lohiya National Law University (Id: U-0511)	SPU	Lucknow	38
35	Dr Shakuntala Misra National Rehabilitation University (Id: U-0512)	SPU	Lucknow	38
36	Indian Institute of Management- Lucknow (Id: U-1008)	IoNI	Lucknow	104
37	Integral University (Id: U-0519)	PU	Lucknow	532
38	King George Medical University (Id: U-0523)	SPU	Lucknow	18
39	Maharishi University of Information Technology (Id: U-0952)	PU	Lucknow	21
40	University of Lucknow (Id: U-0524)	SPU	Lucknow	1638
41	G.L.A University (Id: U-0513)	PU	Mathura	175
42	Sanskriti University (Id: U-0824)	PU	Mathura	23
43	Chaudhary Charan Singh University (Id: U-0506)	SPU	Meerut	2677
44	IIMT University (Id: U-0889)	PU	Meerut	2
45	Shobhit Institute of Engineering & Technology (Id: U-0542)	DUP	Meerut	154
46	IFTM University (Id: U-0515)	PU	Moradabad	250
47	Teerthanker Mahaveer University (Id: U-0544)	PU	Moradabad	124
48	Indian Institute of Information Technology (Id: U-0516)	IoNI	Prayagraj	180
49	Motilal Nehru National Institute of Technology (Id: U-0530)	IoNI	Prayagraj	496
50	Nehru Gram Bharati (Deemed to Be University (Id: U-0532)	DUP	Prayagraj	128
51	Sam Higginbottom Institute of Agriculture, Technology & Sciences (Id: U-0536)	DUGA	Prayagraj	320
52	University Of Allahabad (Id: U-0548)	CU	Prayagraj	2220
53	U.P. Rajarshi Tandon Open University (Id: U-0546)	SOU	Prayagraj	335
54	Mohammad Ali Jauhar University (Id: U-0529)	PU	Rampur	1
55	Glocal University (Id: U-0645)	PU	Saharanpur	33
56	Shobhit University (Id: U-0731)	PU	Saharanpur	28
57	Banaras Hindu University (Id: U-0500)	CU	Varanasi	5329
58	Indian Institute of Technology (Banaras Hindu University (Id: U-0701)	IoNI	Varanasi	628
59	Mahatma Gandhi Kashi Vidyapeeth (Id: U-0527)	SPU	Varanasi	4961

60	Sampurnanand Sanskrit Vishwavidyalaya (Id: U-0537)	SPU	Varanasi	3
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Table 2 reveals that HEIs from 20 districts of Uttar Pradesh are contributing to the Shodhganga repository. The highest number of contributing institutions are located in Lucknow, with 10 HEIs, followed by 9 HEIs from Gautam Buddha Nagar and 6 HEIs from Prayagraj.

5.2 Distribution of ETD contributions to Shodhganga Repository across different categories of HEIs of Uttar Pradesh

Table 3 Type-wise contribution of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) of Uttar Pradesh to the Shodhganga repository

Type of HEIs	No. of ETD contributions on Shodhganga
Central University	17492
Deemed University-Government Aided	1443
Deemed University-Private	676
Institute of National Importance	3163
State Open University	335
State Private University	2980
State Public University	35511
Grand Total	61600

Table 3 data reveal significant variation in contribution levels across different types of HEIs. The total contribution of 61,600 ETDs from Uttar Pradesh demonstrates a strong state-level engagement with Shodhganga. State Public Universities are the leading contributors with 35,511 ETDs, accounting for more than half of the total submissions, followed by Central Universities with 17,492 ETDs. Institutes of National Importance have contributed 3,163 ETDs reflecting a focused yet impactful engagement with the repository, while State Private Universities have collectively submitted 2,980 ETDs, which is notably lower despite their growing numbers in the state. Deemed Universities both government-aided (1,443) and private (676) as well as the State Open University (335) show comparatively lower participation, likely due to its different academic structure and lower focus on conventional research degrees. The data highlights a strong overall engagement from public institutions, while contributions from private and deemed universities remain limited, indicating the need for improved awareness and enforcement of repository submission policies.

5.3 Top 10 HEIs from Uttar Pradesh contributing ETDs to Shodhganga repository.

Table 4 presents the top 10 Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Uttar Pradesh based on the total number of Electronic Theses and Dissertations (ETDs) contributed to the Shodhganga repository, along with the year of their first submission and the duration of their participation. Chatrapati Sahuji Maharaj Kanpur University, Kanpur leads the list with 10,131 ETDs and has

been contributing for 11 years since its first submission in 2011. It is followed closely by Aligarh Muslim University, which has submitted 9,435 ETDs over a span of 9 years (since 2013). Similarly, Banaras Hindu University began its submissions in 2011 and has contributed 5,329 ETDs over 11 years.

Notably, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar University, Agra, with 5,654 ETDs, has achieved this count within just 4 years since it began contributing in 2018. Likewise, Mahatma Gandhi Kashi Vidyapeeth, which started only 3 years ago in 2020, has submitted a remarkable 4,961 ETDs, reflecting high submission intensity in a short period. Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia Awadh University, Ayodhya and Chaudhary Charan Singh University, Meerut have contributed 4,622 and 2,677 ETDs, respectively, over 4 and 9 years. Bundelkhand University, Jhansi and University of Allahabad, Prayagraj, with 2,213 and 2,220 ETDs respectively, have been contributing for over 10 and 7 years. A significant recent contributor is the Academy of Scientific & Innovative Research, Ghaziabad, which joined the repository only in 2022 and has already submitted 1,719 ETDs in less than one year, indicating a strong initial engagement.

This analysis shows that both the longevity of participation and institutional commitment play critical roles in determining overall contribution levels. It also suggests that some newer institutions are demonstrating commendable efforts in catching up with long-term contributors.

Table 4 Top 10 HEIs from Uttar Pradesh contributing ETDs to Shodhganga repository.

Name of HEIs	No. of ETDs Contributed	Date of First Submission	No. of Years since 1st Submission
Chatrapati Sahuji Maharaj Kanpur University, Kanpur	10131	18-05-2011	11
Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh	9435	07-05-2013	09
Dr. B. R. Ambedkar University, Agra	5654	04-12-2018	04
Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi	5329	30-09-2011	11
Mahatma Gandhi Kashi Vidyapeeth, Varanasi	4961	12-02-2020	03
Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia Awadh University, Ayodhya	4622	11-01-2019	04
Chaudhary Charan Singh University, Meerut	2677	17-04-2013	09
University of Allahabad, Prayagraj	2220	15-02-2016	07
Bundelkhand University, Jhansi	2213	06-08-2012	10
Academy of Scientific & Innovative Research, Ghaziabad	1719	06-04-2022	less than 01

5.4 Time Gap in ETD Submissions to the Shodhganga Repository by HEIs in Uttar Pradesh

Figure 1 illustrates the distribution of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Uttar Pradesh based on the time gap (in days) since their last submission of Electronic Theses and Dissertations (ETDs) to the Shodhganga repository, measured up to 15 March 2023. The data has been grouped into 30-day intervals to reflect submission recency more precisely.

The data reveals that the majority of HEIs are actively contributing to the repository. Specifically, 34 HEIs (56.6%) uploaded their most recent ETDs within 0-29 days window, indicating strong recent engagement. Additionally, 11 HEIs (18.3%) fall in the 30-59 days category, suggesting moderate but timely submission activity. Beyond the 60-day mark, there is a noticeable decline in submission activity. Only 5 HEIs last uploaded between 60-89 days ago, collectively showing that 51 out of 60 HEIs (85%) have submitted theses within the last 89 days. As the time since the last upload increases, the number of active institutions drops sharply. Only a handful of HEIs fall into higher time intervals. For instance, 2 institutions Dr. Ram Manohar Lohiya National Law University and Shri Venkateshwara University and last submitted ETDs between 420 to 449 days and 540 to 569 days ago respectively, indicating sporadic or stalled engagement with the repository. Notably, one institution has not uploaded any theses for nearly 870 days, reflecting more than two years of inactivity.

This pattern suggests that while a significant proportion of institutions maintain a regular and recent upload cycle, there is a small subset that shows prolonged inactivity. These gaps may reflect administrative delays, lack of institutional monitoring, or low research throughput.

Figure 1 Distribution of HEIs in Uttar Pradesh by Days Since Last ETD Upload (as of 15 March 2023)

6. Findings and Discussion

The study provides a comprehensive overview of the contribution made by Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Uttar Pradesh to the Shodhganga repository, offering valuable insights into institutional participation, contribution patterns, and gaps in ETD submissions.

One of the key findings is that out of 92 HEIs listed under Uttar Pradesh in the AISHE directory, only 60 (approximately 65%) have contributed Electronic Theses and Dissertations (ETDs) to the Shodhganga repository as of the cut-off date, 15 March 2023. This indicates that despite the UGC mandate, a significant proportion of institutions remain non-participative, highlighting an area of concern in terms of compliance and academic openness.

The district-wise analysis shows that ETD contributions are concentrated in a few academic hubs, with Lucknow, Gautam Buddha Nagar, and Prayagraj accounting for the highest number of contributing HEIs. This concentration may reflect better infrastructural facilities, research output, and administrative support in these regions. In terms of the type of institution, the data shows that State Public Universities are the most active contributors, accounting for over 57% of total submissions (35,511 ETDs). Central Universities follow with 17,492 ETDs, while Institutes of National Importance and State Private Universities contribute far less. The low contribution from Private and Deemed Universities despite their growing presence in the state, suggests gaps in research productivity, repository awareness, or institutional policy enforcement. These disparities point toward the need for strategic outreach, training, and monitoring mechanisms to ensure equitable participation across institutional categories.

The contribution analysis of the top 10 HEIs reveals that both historical presence and recent momentum play crucial roles. Institutions like Chatrapati Sahuji Maharaj Kanpur University and Aligarh Muslim University, with a longer history of participation, have maintained consistently high submission volumes. Meanwhile, some newer entrants such as Mahatma Gandhi Kashi Vidyapeeth and Academy of Scientific & Innovative Research have demonstrated rapid submission growth in a short span, highlighting their strong institutional focus on digital archiving and research visibility. Perhaps most revealing is the analysis of the time gap in submissions. The majority of HEIs (85%) uploaded theses within the last 89 days, indicating an encouraging trend toward regular engagement. However, a small but significant subset of institutions exhibited long gaps ranging from 6 months to over 2 years between uploads. This sporadic participation could stem from administrative inertia, inadequate awareness, or lack of structured research output monitoring. Such inactivity undermines the objective of Shodhganga as a real-time reflection of Indian doctoral research and must be addressed through policy-level initiatives.

Overall, the findings reflect both progress and persisting gaps in the state's engagement with Shodhganga. While several institutions are fully aligned with the repository's goals, a coordinated push is necessary to bring the remaining HEIs into the fold and ensure sustainable, timely, and inclusive contributions across the board.

7. Conclusion

This study highlights the contribution patterns of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Uttar Pradesh to the Shodhganga repository, offering a state-level perspective on digital research dissemination practices. The analysis reveals a generally strong level of participation, particularly from state public and central universities, both of which have consistently submitted ETDs to the repository. However, a substantial number of institutions remain inactive or inconsistent in their engagement, especially among private and deemed universities.

Despite signing a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with INFLIBNET, many universities delayed or did not initiate ETD submissions, reflecting a gap between policy compliance and actual implementation. While a few private universities have signed the MoU, not all have done so, and even among those that have, active participation remains limited. This lack of understanding or prioritization of ETD submission undermines the fundamental purpose of Shodhganga to prevent duplication of academic efforts and to build a reliable, accessible national knowledge repository that supports filtered knowledge creation and social development. The time-gap analysis further reveals that although a majority of contributing HEIs have demonstrated recent activity, a small subset shows prolonged inactivity, suggesting administrative inertia or lack of systematic research output monitoring. To address this, INFLIBNET should proactively expand its MoU coverage to include more HEIs in Uttar Pradesh. Simultaneously, regulatory bodies such as the UGC and university authorities must consider introducing stronger enforcement mechanisms and awareness initiatives to ensure regular and inclusive participation in the national repository.

Bridging the participation gap and promoting consistent engagement across all categories of institutions will not only enhance the visibility of Uttar Pradesh's research output but also contribute meaningfully to India's evolving open-access scholarly communication ecosystem.

References

- About Shodhganga: A reservoir of Indian theses, INFLIBNET Centre.* (2023).
<https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/>
- AISHE- Higher Education Institution Directory.* (2023). [MoE, GoI]. UP, HEI-Directory.
<https://dashboard.aishe.gov.in/hedirectory/#/institutionDirectory/universityDetails/U/ALL>
- Das, S., & Chauhan, V. (2019). Collection of Electronic Theses and Dissertations (ETDs) among state universities of Gujarat: A study. *International Journal of Information Studies & Libraries*, 4(1), 22–29.
- Dey, S., & Das, D. (2021). Exploring the ETDs on Shodhganga project: A detailed study on the State Universities of West Bengal. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-Journal)*, 6035, 1–15.
- Esh, M., & Ghosh, S. (2021). Role in contribution to open access repository by the Northeast universities in India. *DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology*, 41(6), 448–454.
<https://doi.org/10.14429/djlit.41.6.17027>
- Gupta, D. K., & Gupta, N. (2014). Analytical study of the ETD repositories and government initiatives for depositing ETDs in India. *Library Management*, 35(4/5), 308–319.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/LM-09-2013-0092>
- Jhamb, G., & Samim, A. (2017). Contribution to open access repository by the central universities of India: A case study of Shodhganga. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-Journal)*, 1559, 1–19.
- Katagi, S., & Kumbar, B. D. (2022). Contribution to national repository of electronic theses and dissertations by the Universities of Karnataka: A case study of Shodhganga. *The Journal of Indian Library Association*, 58(1), 44–60.
- Sandhya, R. S. (2019). Electronic theses and dissertations contributed by Indian universities to Shodhganga: A case study of Osmania University, Hyderabad. *Pearl: A Journal of Library and Information Science*, 13(1), 45–52.
- Siddiqui, I. A. (2020). Participation of Indian law universities in Shodhganga: An analytical study. *Journal of Library and Information Communication Technology*, 9(1), 51–56.
- Singh, B. P. (2019). Electronic thesis and dissertations (ETD) submission at Shodhganga repository by Indian universities: An evaluative study. *International Journal of Information, Library & Society*, 8(2), 47–57.
- Verma, M. K., Yadav, S. K., & Singh, S. N. (2017). Mapping the contribution to Shodhganga by central universities of India in LIS research: An evaluation. *International Journal of Library Management and Services*, 4(2), 14–24.